

Appendix D: Target overview table

Here, we provide all relevant information of the targets studied in this work. We sort them in two tables, Table 1 with the binaries and candidates, and Table 2 with the RV constant objects.

Appendix E: Notes on individual targets classified as binaries

BLOeM 1-040: BLOeM 1-040 is an O9.7 III:n e star according to Paper I. Using all available He I lines to measure RVs, we find that two epochs of the target meet both binary criteria described in Sect. 3.2. The RV threshold of 20 km s^{-1} is barely met, with a $\Delta RV_{\text{max}} = 22 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (see Fig. 1a). Given their broadening and the low S/N ratio, we refrain from measuring the RVs of the He II lines. The double-peaked emission lines follow the same trend in RVs than the He I absorption lines and also indicate a binary with a period of approximately 45 days. The shift in RV measured in He I and Balmer lines is within the uncertainty of the RVs measured in the reference epoch (epoch 7).

BLOeM 1-113: BLOeM 1-113 was classified as B1 II e in Paper I. It shows the signature of an SB2 with the narrow, non-variable, clean He I absorption lines moving in apparent anti-phase with the weak emission lines, which additionally show intrinsic variability. The maximum RV amplitude ΔRV_{max} is similar for both absorption and emission lines and is around 40 km s^{-1} . The RV curve and spectra at RV extremes are shown in Figures 2a and 2b.

BLOeM 2-021: This target was assigned a spectral type of B2.5: II: e (Paper I). Here, based on the He I lines, we classify the star as binary with a ΔRV_{max} of 25 km s^{-1} (Fig. 3a). The emission lines, which are double-peaked and strong in particular in H γ (Fig. 3b) do not show any significant RV variations. The slight trend visible in anti-phase especially visible in epochs 3-5 might be spurious, and will be further investigated with additional epochs.

BLOeM 2-066: The spectral type assigned to this object in Paper I is O9.7 III:nnn pe+, indicating that the object is a rapid rotator. The spectra of BLOeM 2-066 are on average fairly noisy. The He I lines show a signature that could be interpreted as SB2, while the He II are too broad and noisy to measure reliable RVs. The emission component is a complicated superposition of several components, with the strongest clearly shifting in wavelength (see Fig. 4a). With a ΔRV_{max} of 50 km s^{-1} in He I and almost 60 km s^{-1} in H γ and the potential SB2 signature, BLOeM 2-066 is definitely a binary. To measure the RVs more accurately, as well as to assess whether it is a genuine SB2 requires more observations. The tentative RV curve and spectra at RV extremes are shown in Figures 4a and 4b, which have to be taken with a grain of salt.

BLOeM 2-082: BLOeM 2-082 is one of the Oe stars in the sample with a spectral type O9.2 III pe (Paper I). Given the overall low S/N in the spectra, the determined RVs, especially from the broad He I and He II lines, have large error bars (see Fig. 5a). The double-peaked Balmer emission lines, however, show a clear trend over time, with a peak-to-peak RV amplitude of almost 45 km s^{-1} . Based on the large amplitude and the clear trend in RVs, we classify BLOeM 2-082 as a binary. It was detected as a

binary already in the RIOTS survey (Lamb et al. 2016), and coincides with an X-ray source (Evans et al. 2010; Antoniou et al. 2019), making it a HMXB.

BLOeM 2-109: This target shows comparatively narrow He I absorption lines (see Fig. 6b) and was classified as B2 II e (Paper I). The RVs measured from the absorption lines show a clear sinusoidal trend with a maximum amplitude of around 40 km s^{-1} (see Fig. 6a) the observed time seems to cover almost exactly half of the binary period, indicating that the period of the binary system is around 60 days. The RVs measured from the weak, double-peaked emission line in H γ follow these measurements closely.

BLOeM 2-111: This target shows only weak emission lines with a single peak. The RVs measured from narrow He I lines and the weak emission in H γ indicate anti-phase motion, which is why we classify it as SB2. The peak-to-peak RV amplitude of 17 km s^{-1} measured in the He I lines is below the imposed threshold of 20 km s^{-1} . While the one measured in H γ is larger, it is not significant due to the larger error bars. The RV curve and spectra at RV extremes are shown in Figs. 7a and 7b.

BLOeM 5-069: This object was classified as B3 II e and shows the typical spectrum of a shell Be star (i.e., broad absorption lines, with additional emission components in the Balmer lines superimposed with narrow absorption features, see Fig. 8b). Those features are interpreted as a Be star viewed almost equator-on, where the narrow absorption component arises in the disk along the line of sight. The He I lines indicate BLOeM 5-069 to be a binary, with a maximum RV amplitude of 42 km s^{-1} . The RVs of the emission component alone are difficult to measure and dominated by the stationary strong absorption.

BLOeM 5-071: For this particular target, classified as SB2 with an O8.5: Ib and an OB pe component in Paper I, we use the Si IV line at 4088.3 \AA to estimate RVs as the line is clean and not variable. Most other lines (apart from the more noisy He II lines) are impacted by strong emission (see Fig. 9b). BLOeM 5-071 shows a similar signature as BLOeM 3-031, with strongly moving absorption lines ($\Delta RV_{\text{max}} = 164 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) and a fairly stable emission line component (Fig. 9a). Again, the formal RV errors are of the order of a few km s^{-1} but hardly visible due to the large amplitude of the RVs. The origin of the emission as well as the nature of the binary remains to be determined.

BLOeM 6-001: This object was classified as B0.5 III ,e in Paper I. Based on the two above mentioned criteria and the RVs measured from the He I lines, it is classified as binary. One epoch stands out (epoch 7, see Figs. 10a and 10b), which also corresponds to the epoch with the lowest S/N. To ensure that the binary classification is not solely based on one spurious, potentially low-quality measurement, we re-evaluate if the criteria are met when removing this particular epoch. Given that this is true, we classify BLOeM 6-001 as a binary. The H γ line indicates a similar trend, with a maximum amplitude ΔRV_{max} just below the threshold of 20 km s^{-1} .

BLOeM 7-013: This system was classified as B1.5 III e. The stable absorption lines show radial velocity variations with a

Table 1: Parameter summary of all binaries and candidate binaries. The columns give the BLOeM ID, the Gaia DR3 ID, coordinates, and G-band magnitude, and the spectral type from Paper 1. The maximum RV amplitude between two epochs is given in column ΔRV_{\max} . The columns ‘C1’ and ‘C2’ indicate if the system satisfies the two binary criteria described in Sect. 3.2. The binary status is given in status (‘bin’ indicates stars classified as binaries, while ‘cand’ indicates candidates). Additional information on the type of binary and the literature are given in the last two columns.

BLOeM ID	Gaia DR3 ID	RA [J2000]	DEC [J2000]	G [mag]	SpT	ΔRV_{\max} [km s^{-1}]	C1	C2	status	type	literature
BLOeM 1-040	4690525438865707904	15.6657917	-71.9966111	13.48	O9.7 III:n:e	22.0 ± 4.9	T	T	bin	SB1	
BLOeM 1-113	4690511626248698368	16.2209167	-71.9886389	14.16	B1 II:e	42.4 ± 3.5	T	T	bin	SB2	
BLOeM 2-021	4688964922657391744	12.7445833	-72.7626944	14.39	B2.5: II:e	25.2 ± 3.7	T	T	bin	SB2	
BLOeM 2-066	4688966739421000448	13.1017083	-72.6775278	14.03	O9.7 III:nnn pe+	50.0 ± 9.5	T	T	bin	?	
BLOeM 2-082	4685960021758355584	13.2179167	-72.8083889	14.6	O9.2 III:pe	39.9 ± 12.2	T	T	bin	?	HMXB ^{1,6}
BLOeM 2-109	4688990692466513408	13.4242917	-72.6228056	14.84	B2 II:e	41.7 ± 2.7	T	T	bin	SB1	
BLOeM 2-111	4685983699984262912	13.463875	-72.7545556	14.62	B2 II:e	17.3 ± 3.0	T	F	bin	SB2	
BLOeM 5-069	4687502400374028928	16.5525	-72.2153611	14.37	B3 II:e	42.3 ± 5.2	T	T	bin	SB2?	
BLOeM 5-071	4687437254305162880	16.57175	-72.4629722	13.28	O8.5: Ib + OBpe	164.5 ± 4.9	T	T	bin	SB2?	
BLOeM 6-001	4687162582543422080	18.123875	-73.2916111	14.32	B0.5 III:e	36.2 ± 6.6	T	T	bin	?	
BLOeM 7-013	4685988544708868864	14.5094583	-72.6315556	14.51	B1.5 III:e	44.7 ± 5.4	T	T	bin	SB2?	
BLOeM 7-045	4685993419427102848	14.8115	-72.5156944	16.41	B2 III:e	67.6 ± 15.9	T	T	bin	?	
BLOeM 7-082	4687491164738701056	15.2446667	-72.5139444	13.78	B2 e+	42.4 ± 2.2	T	T	bin	SB2	
BLOeM 7-114	4687475118738255616	15.510875	-72.6196111	15.27	B2 II:e	38.1 ± 5.3	T	T	bin	-	
BLOeM 1-058	4690512313443855360	15.749	-72.0798889	13.53	O9.5 II:pe	34.6 ± 10.8	F	T	cand	?	
BLOeM 2-056	4688981106097035008	12.9828333	-72.5343333	13.88	B2 II:e	17.9 ± 3.1	T	F	cand	?	
BLOeM 2-070	4688962414395649792	13.144625	-72.7636111	14.46	B1 II:e	20.0 ± 1.9	T	F	cand	?	
BLOeM 2-071	4688968049392847488	13.148375	-72.6311389	14.51	B1.5 II:e	16.6 ± 2.6	T	F	cand	SB1	
BLOeM 2-097	4689003680451206272	13.2900417	-72.5631111	14.41	B5 II:e	11.3 ± 5.4	F	F	cand	SB1	
BLOeM 4-113	4690502761435017984	15.4837083	-72.1746389	15.02	B2.5 II:pe	18.4 ± 4.4	T	F	cand	SB1	HMXB ^{1,2,3}
BLOeM 5-035	4687482780961207424	16.3032083	-72.485	14.87	B1.5 II:e	14.1 ± 4.8	F	F	cand	-	
BLOeM 5-115	4687460481482120832	17.1076667	-72.3909167	13.9	O9.5: V:pe	26.6 ± 7.6	T	T	cand	SB2?	
BLOeM 7-051	4685990434494050048	14.85675	-72.5381944	15.53	B1 II:e	16.0 ± 8.4	F	F	cand	-	
BLOeM 8-021	4689032851851488000	13.0053333	-72.4025	14.19	O7 V-IIIInn pe	23.3 ± 22.4	F	T	cand	?	
BLOeM 8-059	4689061748394242944	13.2452083	-72.2081667	15.34	B2 II:e	29.4 ± 7.5	F	T	cand	?	
BLOeM 3-031	4685836708972891648	11.8871667	-73.3545278	14.03	B0: III: + OBe	523.9 ± 4.2	T	T	bin	SB2; IB	EB*
BLOeM 6-034	4686408313260119552	18.7012083	-73.3825278	14.74	B2 III-II:e	61.0 ± 2.6	F	T	bin	SB2; IB	EB*

* classification based on OGLE-III photometry from Pawlak et al. (2013). X-ray source identifications are from ¹: Evans et al. (2010), ²: Sturm et al. (2013), ³: Wang et al. (2016), ⁴: Laycock et al. (2010), ⁵: Traulsen et al. (2020), ⁶: Antoniou & Zezas (2016)

Table 2: Parameter summary of all RV-stable stars classified as presumably-single stars here. The columns give the BLOeM ID, the Gaia DR3 ID, coordinates, and G-band magnitude, and the spectral type from [Paper I](#). The maximum RV amplitude between two epochs is given in column ΔRV_{\max} . Additional information from the literature are given in the last column.

BLOeM ID	Gaia DR3 ID	RA [J2000]	DEC [J2000]	G [mag]	SpT	ΔRV_{\max} [km s ⁻¹]	literature
BLOeM 1-018	4690506025610129152	15.38575	-72.1548056	14.52	B2 II: e	7.0 ± 3.0	
BLOeM 1-063	4690509289786901504	15.7671667	-72.0950278	16.12	B1.5 II: e	24.6 ± 7.4	
BLOeM 1-073	4690526057340871040	15.8425	-71.9436667	14.72	B1 II: e	4.6 ± 2.7	
BLOeM 1-075	4690526057340870272	15.8544167	-71.9432778	13.67	O9.2 II:n pe	16.5 ± 7.7	
BLOeM 1-079	4690512828839860096	15.870125	-72.0428611	14.02	O9.2 III:(n) pe	18.2 ± 14.1	
BLOeM 1-106	4687505801988031232	16.0892083	-72.1541389	13.44	B1.5 e	14.0 ± 5.2	
BLOeM 2-017	4688982652297652352	12.7055833	-72.55875	14.55	B2 II e	8.9 ± 6.9	
BLOeM 2-018	4688966090888390784	12.706875	-72.7110556	14.13	O6.5 III: e?	7.8 ± 2.4	
BLOeM 2-055	4688984061034529408	12.9714167	-72.5301944	14.86	O9.7 V:n e	38.0 ± 10.1	HMXB ^{1,3,4,5,6}
BLOeM 2-061	4688961894666576768	13.027375	-72.82975	14.84	B2 II: e	10.7 ± 5.2	
BLOeM 2-063	4688963204681907328	13.0646667	-72.7644444	14.69	B2 III e	7.4 ± 2.8	
BLOeM 2-081	4688968461709335040	13.216625	-72.5858056	14.45	B2 II e	19.8 ± 6.3	
BLOeM 2-104	4688987252155037568	13.3747917	-72.6957222	14.07	O5.5 f? pe	11.9 ± 4.3	
BLOeM 3-011	4685854369881566848	11.715875	-73.1590556	14.46	B0.5 III: e	19.1 ± 4.5	
BLOeM 3-016	4685849044122619264	11.7389583	-73.3024444	16.18	B2 III e	23.7 ± 10.3	
BLOeM 3-018	4685836635962991104	11.7675833	-73.3698056	14.39	B1.5: II: e	15.1 ± 6.2	EB*
BLOeM 3-025	4685850242400168960	11.8104583	-73.2306111	14.71	B2 II e	6.9 ± 5.5	
BLOeM 3-027	4685948515603957376	11.841	-73.1140278	13.94	B1.5 II e	8.6 ± 4.5	
BLOeM 3-035	4685835884339216512	11.9025833	-73.3803611	15.88	B2 II e	12.0 ± 8.5	
BLOeM 3-040	4685942949325301120	11.949375	-73.2571667	14.45	B2 II: e+	23.5 ± 10.3	
BLOeM 3-062	4685948064629440768	12.100625	-73.1136389	14.05	O9.7 II e	17.1 ± 3.1	
BLOeM 3-077	4685947828409081088	12.2034167	-73.1056944	14.34	B1 II e	10.2 ± 5.0	
BLOeM 3-095	4685925833826106368	12.3962917	-73.3891111	15.83	B2 II: e	70.0 ± 18.4	
BLOeM 3-098	4685931679327948800	12.4280833	-73.2883889	14.44	O6 V((f))n e	34.0 ± 16.3	
BLOeM 3-107	4685880277148119040	12.5162083	-73.4038056	14.0	O9.7 II:(n) e?	12.7 ± 4.1	
BLOeM 4-002	4689016049958328576	14.4050833	-72.21925	13.47	B1.5: e	11.6 ± 3.0	
BLOeM 4-010	4689016221756877184	14.5416667	-72.1838889	13.41	B1 e+	3.1 ± 1.2	
BLOeM 4-022	4689015500202439296	14.6777917	-72.2128056	14.86	B2.5 II: e	27.1 ± 10.6	
BLOeM 4-026	4689015328403760128	14.696125	-72.2171389	14.55	O9.5 III pe	14.6 ± 7.4	HMXB ^{1,6}
BLOeM 4-034	4689015736378946688	14.7764583	-72.1655833	14.2	B2 II pe	14.8 ± 4.7	
BLOeM 4-035	4689016771512472960	14.7767083	-72.1291667	14.86	B3 II: e	15.4 ± 6.2	
BLOeM 4-039	4690521006458654464	14.7915417	-72.09675	14.42	O6.5 f? pe	4.0 ± 2.5	
BLOeM 4-071	4690504926098661504	14.9639167	-72.1912778	14.31	O9.7 II: e?	8.3 ± 2.6	
BLOeM 5-020	4687486526172590720	16.1969583	-72.43325	14.55	B1.5 II e	11.2 ± 6.6	
BLOeM 5-023	4687487247726980864	16.2099167	-72.3830278	14.66	B1.5 III e	5.7 ± 2.8	
BLOeM 5-031	4687487007208845056	16.2723333	-72.3996667	14.39	B2.5: II: e	9.5 ± 3.9	
BLOeM 5-034	4687486938489379328	16.296875	-72.4046389	14.19	B1.5 II: e	13.0 ± 5.2	
BLOeM 5-046	4687483777393718400	16.423125	-72.4344444	13.95	B1.5 II: e	13.3 ± 7.2	
BLOeM 5-047	4687502228575362688	16.4250833	-72.2226111	15.14	B2.5 III: e	5.9 ± 4.9	
BLOeM 5-066	4687489824707171456	16.5262917	-72.3009722	13.74	B2 II: e+	10.8 ± 1.7	
BLOeM 5-089	4687437494823799168	16.7412083	-72.4588611	15.55	B2 III: e	24.1 ± 8.5	
BLOeM 5-092	4687437529183051136	16.7741667	-72.4521667	14.2	B1 II: pe	16.6 ± 3.0	
BLOeM 5-094	4687485976416952832	16.7946667	-72.343	15.07	B1 e	12.1 ± 3.7	
BLOeM 6-011	4687160280440948608	18.412	-73.2968333	15.42	B2 III: e	15.7 ± 6.1	
BLOeM 6-113	4686415430023013760	19.3270417	-73.2979444	14.44	O nnpe	14.3 ± 14.7	
BLOeM 7-037	4685974457212254336	14.72675	-72.7313056	15.02	B1.5 III: e	15.7 ± 5.7	
BLOeM 7-038	4685975213126426368	14.7310833	-72.717	14.65	B0 II: e	7.9 ± 2.7	
BLOeM 7-047	4685975625443431808	14.8423333	-72.7536667	14.75	B0.2 III: pe	16.6 ± 6.4	
BLOeM 7-078	4687491886293188608	15.1855	-72.4973056	13.85	B0 e	13.3 ± 4.6	
BLOeM 7-093	4687477592639651072	15.3257083	-72.6415	15.47	B2 II e	13.1 ± 7.0	
BLOeM 8-035	4689074461499247744	13.0714167	-72.1463333	12.99	O9.7 III: e	10.3 ± 5.0	
BLOeM 8-043	4689057934463327616	13.1410417	-72.2833056	14.91	B2 II: e+	12.5 ± 7.4	
BLOeM 8-064	4689056628793468928	13.3026667	-72.3415833	15.22	B3 II e	16.3 ± 4.1	
BLOeM 8-100	4689009070622046336	13.5451667	-72.3691389	15.46	B2 II e	17.1 ± 7.7	
BLOeM 8-109	4689011754988965888	13.5939167	-72.2859444	14.1	B0 III: pe	22.4 ± 12.7	

* classification based on OGLE-III photometry from [Pawlak et al. \(2013\)](#). X-ray source identifications are from ¹: [Evans et al. \(2010\)](#), ²: [Sturm et al. \(2013\)](#), ³: [Wang et al. \(2016\)](#), ⁴ [Laycock et al. \(2010\)](#), ⁵ [Traulsen et al. \(2020\)](#), ⁶ [Antoniou & Zezas \(2016\)](#)

maximum amplitude of 45 km s^{-1} . The weak, single-peaked emission line shows no significant variation based on the epochs obtained so far. The emission feature is not located in the center of the line, and appears stable on the covered timescales, potentially implying that the feature stems from nebular contamination and the object is not a "true" OBe star. Figures 11a and 11b show the RV curve and the spectra at the RV extremes.

BLOeM 7-045: This rapidly rotating B2 III: e star (see Paper I) shows only weak emission in H γ . The broad and noisy lines make it difficult to measure RVs, and the estimated formal errors may be underestimated. Formally, the measured RVs fulfill both criteria with a peak-to-peak amplitude $>65 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, it is thus classified as binary. The RV curve as well as the spectra at RV extremes for BLOeM 7-045 are shown in Figs. 12a and 12b.

BLOeM 7-082: This system, also called AzV 261, was previously classified as blue supergiant and its spectroscopic and photometric variability was investigated by Kalari et al. (2018), searching for additional luminous blue variable (LBV)-like stars. While the authors found strong photometric variability in this object, they concluded that BLOeM 7-082 is not an LBV-like object as it does not show variations in its spectral type.

In Paper I, we classified the star as B2 e+, based on narrow, clean He I absorption lines as well as OBe-typical double-peaked emission lines. Based on the RVs measured from He I lines, which show a maximum amplitude of 45 km s^{-1} , we classify the system as binary. The strong but variable emission lines also show RV variations that appear to be in anti-phase with the absorption lines, with a similar amplitude. The binary status of this system might explain the photometric variability reported in Kalari et al. (2018), which requires a more detailed investigation in the future.

BLOeM 7-114: This target was classified as B2 II e in Paper I. Based on the RVs measured from the noisy but fairly narrow He I lines (see Fig. 14b) we classify BLOeM 7-114 as binary. The RV curve (see Fig. 14a) shows RV amplitudes of up to almost 40 km s^{-1} and indicates a period shorter than the three months covered by observations so far. Additional epochs will help to constrain this further.

Appendix F: Notes on candidate binaries

BLOeM 1-058 : This object is one of the Oe stars, with spectral type O9.5 II: pe (Paper I). The overall spectra are quite noisy and due to the broad lines as well as strong emission lines, RVs of clean absorption lines are difficult to measure and have large error bars (see Fig. 15b). While the RVs from emission lines as well as He II show no significant variability, the He I absorption lines (the ones not impacted by the emission) fulfill the second binary criteria (Fig. 15a). However, given the low data quality as well as the mismatch between He I and He II RVs we classify this object as candidate binary.

BLOeM 2-056: This target, a B2 II: e star according to Paper I, shows RV variations with a maximum amplitude of approximately 15 km s^{-1} (see Fig. 16b). As the measured RVs seem to indicate a long-term anti-phase trend between Balmer and He I that is reminiscent of a binary orbit (Fig. 16a), we classify this

object as candidate binary that requires additional observations to be confirmed.

BLOeM 2-070: This star was classified as B1 II e in Paper I. The spectrum, in particular the He I lines of the star, show variability (Fig. 17b). The RVs measured from those indicate, that the target is a binary, with a maximum amplitude of 20 km s^{-1} (Fig. 17a), thus just at the imposed threshold. The changes in the shape of the lines, which occur mostly in the line core, while the overall line seems stable, however, might indicate the variability observed here stems from line-profile variability (LPV) typical for pulsating OBe stars. We thus classify BLOeM 2-070 as candidate binary.

BLOeM 2-071: Only four epochs are available for this object. It is similar to the star discussed before, with a spectral type of B1.5 II: e (Paper I), and the He I lines show variability that could either be indicative of LPVs or binarity (Fig. 18b). Given that the He I RVs as well as the H γ RVs lines show the same trend, but the maximum RV amplitude does not exceed the 20 km s^{-1} threshold (Fig. 18a), we classify BLOeM 2-071 as candidate binary.

BLOeM 2-097: This star is the target with the latest spectral type in the sample, it was classified as B5 II e. While the maximum RV amplitude ΔRV_{max} measured from the He I lines is only 11 km s^{-1} (Fig. 19b) and thus below the imposed RV threshold, the RV curves measured both from He I lines and H γ show a clear downwards trend over the covered observing period (see Fig. 19a). We thus classify the object as candidate binary, which might be confirmed by subsequent epochs.

BLOeM 4-113: This B2.5 II pe star, which shows double-peaked emission in H γ (see Fig. 20b), would by eye be classified as a binary with a period of at least 100 days (at least twice the observing span, see Fig. 20a). However, the maximum RV amplitude $\Delta RV_{\text{max}}=20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ is just below the imposed threshold of 20 km s^{-1} and thus the star is formally not listed as binary here. It will, however, most likely fulfill the second criterion when additional epochs are available, and is thus listed as binary candidate here. It seems to further coincide with an X-ray source (see e.g., Evans et al. 2010; Sturm et al. 2013), which would make it a BeXRB.

BLOeM 5-035: this star has a spectral type of B1.5 II: e. The emission lines are quite weak and, combined with the low S/N not suitable to estimate RVs. The He I RV curve of BLOeM 5-035 shows an upwards trend over time that can be interpreted as potential binary motion (Fig. 21a). However, the measured maximum RV amplitude is only 14 km s^{-1} (see Fig. 21b), and the system therefore does not meet both binary criteria. Because of the trend, we however classify it as candidate binary.

BLOeM 5-115: This target was also classified as Oe star in Paper I, in particular as O9.5 V: pe star. The star is formally classified as binary as the He I RVs fulfill the RV criteria. The He II RVs however do not agree with them, and have large error bars (see Fig. 22a). The strong emission in Balmer lines seems to be stable. Given the binary nature of this object is not convincing, we classify it as candidate binary and await further observations to constrain the nature better.

Fig. 1a: RV curve of BLOeM 1-040.

Fig. 1b: RV extremes of BLOeM 1-040.

Fig. 2a: RV curve of BLOeM 1-113.

Fig. 2b: RV extremes of BLOeM 1-113.

Fig. 3a: RV curve of BLOeM 2-021.

Fig. 3b: RV extremes of BLOeM 2-021.

Fig. 4a: RV curve of BLOeM2-066.

Fig. 4b: RV extremes of BLOeM2-066.

Fig. 5a: RV curve of BLOeM2-082.

Fig. 5b: RV extremes of BLOeM2-082.

Fig. 6a: RV curve of BLOeM2-109.

Fig. 6b: RV extremes of BLOeM2-109.

Fig. 7a: RV curve of BLOeM2-111.

Fig. 7b: RV extremes of BLOeM2-111.

Fig. 8a: RV curve of BLOeM5-069.

Fig. 8b: RV extremes of BLOeM5-069.

Fig. 9a: RV curve of BLOeM5-071.

Fig. 9b: RV extremes of BLOeM5-071.

Fig. 10a: RV curve of BLOeM 6-001.

Fig. 10b: RV extremes of BLOeM 6-001.

Fig. 11a: RV curve of BLOeM 7-013.

Fig. 11b: RV extremes of BLOeM 7-013.

Fig. 12a: RV curve of BLOeM 7-045.

Fig. 12b: RV extremes of BLOeM 7-045.

Fig. 13a: RV curve of BLOeM 7-082.

Fig. 13b: RV extremes of BLOeM 7-082.

Fig. 14a: RV curve of BLOeM 7-114.

Fig. 14b: RV extremes of BLOeM 7-114.

BLOeM 7-051: This star is also a rapidly rotating B-type star with a spectral type B1 II:e (Paper I). It shows potential weak emission infilling in the wings of H γ , too weak to measure RVs. Given the broad lines and the relatively low S/N, the RVs measured from He I do not fulfill the binary criteria. The RV curve (Fig. 23a), however appears to show a sinusoidal trend. The spectra at the measured RV extremes are shown in Fig. 23b.

BLOeM 8-021: This target is an Oe star with spectral type O7 V-IIIInn,pe (Paper I). The spectrum of this object is very noisy and the spectral lines are broad, thus the RVs measured from absorption have large error bars (of the order of 10 km s⁻¹). Additionally, some He I lines are impacted by emission and cannot be used to estimate RVs. As the RVs measured from He II lines formally fulfill both binarity criteria, we classify this target as candidate binary, however note that no similar signature is detected in He I or Balmer emission lines. The RV curve and the spectra at RV extremes for BLOeM 8-082 are shown in Figs. 24a and 24b.

BLOeM 8-059: Based on the two binary criteria imposed in this work, BLOeM 8-059 is classified as a binary from the RV measurements of the He I lines (see Figs. 25a and 25b). However, given that the S/N ratio in the spectra is low, and the measured RVs would indicate a very short period, we conservatively classify this object as binary candidate.

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Fig. 15a: RV curve of BLOeM 1-058.

Fig. 15b: RV extremes of BLOeM 1-058.

Fig. 16a: RV curve of BLOeM 2-056.

Fig. 16b: RV extremes of BLOeM 2-056.

Fig. 17a: RV curve of BLOeM 2-070.

Fig. 17b: RV extremes of BLOeM 2-070.

Fig. 18a: RV curve of BLOeM 2-071.

Fig. 18b: RV extremes of BLOeM 2-071.

Fig. 19a: RV curve of BLOeM 2-097.

Fig. 19b: RV extremes of BLOeM 2-097.

Fig. 20a: RV curve of BLOeM 4-113.

Fig. 20b: RV extremes of BLOeM 4-113.

Fig. 21a: RV curve of BLOeM 5-035.

Fig. 21b: RV extremes of BLOeM 5-035.

Fig. 22a: RV curve of BLOeM 5-115.

Fig. 22b: RV extremes of BLOeM 5-115.

Fig. 23a: RV curve of BLOeM 7-051.

Fig. 23b: RV extremes of BLOeM 7-051.

Fig. 24a: RV curve of BLOeM 8-021.

Fig. 24b: RV extremes of BLOeM 8-021.

Fig. 25a: RV curve of BLOeM 8-059.

Fig. 25b: RV extremes of BLOeM 8-059.